

Key to species of the genus *Homalocephala* Zetterstedt 1838 (Diptera: Ulidiidae)

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Kameneva, E. P. & Korneyev, V. A. Key to species of the genus *Homalocephala* Zetterstedt 1838 (Diptera: Ulidiidae). Abstract. The genus *Homalocephala* is a member of the tribe Seiopterini occurring in the Holarctics. Larvae of these flies live under the bark of fallen deciduous and coniferous trees. An illustrated key to adults of seven Holarctic species is provided.

Key words: Diptera, Ulidiidae, Seiopterini, *Homalocephala*, key.

Каменєва, Е. П. і Корнєєв, В. А. Таблиця для визначення видів роду *Homalocephala* Zetterstedt 1838 (Diptera: Ulidiidae). Резюме. Рід *Homalocephala* належить до триби Сеїоптеріні, поширеної в Голарктиці. Личинки цих мух живуть під корою листяних та хвойних дерев. Наведено ключ для визначення імаго семи видів роду, що зустрічаються в Голарктиці.

Key words: Diptera, Ulidiidae, Seiopterini, *Homalocephala*, таблиця для визначення.

Каменєва, Е. П. и Корнєєв, В. А. Определительная таблица видов рода *Homalocephala* Zetterstedt 1838 (Diptera: Ulidiidae). Резюме. Род *Homalocephala* принадлежит к трибе Сеїоптеріні, распространенной в Голарктике. Личинки этих мух живут под корой лиственных и хвойных деревьев. Приведен ключ для определения имаго семи видов рода, встречающихся в Голарктике.

Key words: Diptera, Ulidiidae, Seiopterini, *Homalocephala*, определительная таблица.

The genus *Homalocephala* is a member of a small tribe Seiopterini (Kameneva & Korneyev 1994, 1995, 2006) occurring in the Holarctics and represented mainly by xylophylous species.

Since the last published illustrated key (Andersson, 1991), numerous additional data on synonymy and distribution were published (Krivosheina, Krivosheina 1996, 1997; Kameneva 2001, 2008), but no comprehensive key to *Homalocephala* species has been published yet.

Genus *Homalocephala* Zetterstedt 1838

Type species: *Homalocephala albitarsis* Zetterstedt 1838 (by monotypy).

Syn. *Psairoptera* Wahlberg 1838.

Type species: *Psairoptera biumbrata* Wahlberg 1838 (by subsequent designation of Andersson 1991).

Homalocephala includes seven species, which occur in the nemoral zones of the Holarctics (North of Europe and North America, Siberia and Far East of Asia, Alps and Caucasus). Larvae live under the bark of fallen coniferous (larches, pines, pseudotsugas) and especially deciduous (aspens, birches, poplars, willows) trees (Lukasheva, 1987; Krivosheina, Krivosheina, 1996).

Andersson (1991) reviewed Fennoscandian species, including revision of Zetterstedt's and Wahlberg's species type material. Krivosheina & Krivosheina (1996, 1997) reviewed the species occurring in Russia, with numerous records from Siberia and Far East, described two new species from Russia, and summarized known data on the larval biology. Kameneva (2002, 2008) provided additional new records and synonymies based on studies of New and Old World type and non-type material.

Key to species

1. Halteres light yellow. (Wings as on Figs 1–5). 2
- Halteres dark brown. (Wing as on Fig. 6). 6
2. Vein R_1 setulose in apical portion. Face white, flattened, with poorly expressed carina in dorsal portion and antennal grooves (Figs 9–10). Katepisternum white microtrichose and white setulose. Wing with proximal margin of apical spot more or less perpendicular to R_{2+3} vein (Figs 2–3). 3

- Vein R_1 setulose throughout its whole length. Face brown, with clearly expressed medial carina (Figs 7–8). Katepisternum white microtrichose and short black setulose. Wing with proximal margin of apical spot subparallel to wing apical margin or this spot is faint (Fig. 1). Fennoscandia, European Russia, Caucasus, Siberia. *H. angustata* (Wahlberg 1838)
3. Wing with two small dark spots: first in pterostigma only, second (around apex of R_{2+3}) not reaching M (Figs 2–3). Wing in posterior half uniformly white microtrichose. Scutellum and female tergosternite 7 matt, light whitish pollinose. 4
- Wing as a rule with 2 large dark spots those reach at least R_{4+5} , first between pterostigma and r-m crossvein, and second between R_{2+3} apex and M vein (Figs 4–5); if the first one not reaching r-m, then scutellum and female tergosternite 7 shining, non-pollinose. Wing in posterior half often with dark microtrichia. Apices of surstyli incurved. 5
4. Palp black. Wing with apical spot aligned to wing apical margin from R_{2+3} almost to M (Fig. 3). Far East Russia. *H. ozerovi* Krivosheina & Krivosheina 1997
- Palp reddish. Wing with apical spot reaching R_{4+5} but distal margin mostly separated from wing apical margin (Fig. 2). Northern and Central part of Europe, Caucasus, Siberia, Canada, and North of the USA. *H. albitarsis* Zetterstedt 1838
- Syn. *Ortalis diopsides* Walker, 1849; *Ortalis costalis* Walker, 1849; *Psairoptera bipunctata* Loew 1854.
5. Femora and tarsi reddish yellow. Wing with apical spot reaching R_{4+5} but distal margin mostly separated from wing apical margin (Fig. 4). *H. bimaculata* (Wahlberg 1838)
- Femora and tarsi reddish dark brown. Wing with apical spot aligned to wing apical margin from R_{2+3} to R_{4+5} (Fig. 5). Northern and Central Europe. *H. biumbrata* Wahlberg
6. Katepisternum and anepisternum matt, grey microtrichose, without longer setulae (Fig. 11). Face uniformly whitish to its ventral margin (Fig. 11). Flagellomere 1 dark brown. Fennoscandia, Caucasus, Siberia (from Buryatia to Kamchatka), and Canada. *H. apicalis* (Wahlberg 1838)
- Syn. *Psairoptera biseta* Frey, 1909, *Psairoptera similis* Cresson, 1924
- Katepisternum and anepisternum shining, long brown setulose. Face with narrowly brown ventral margin. Flagellomere 1 reddish. Alps, Fennoscandia, Siberia, North America. *H. mamaevi* Krivosheina et Krivosheina 1996

Figs 1–6. Wings of *Homalocephala*: 1 — *H. angustata*; 2 — *H. albitarsis*; 3 — *H. ozerovi*; 4 — *H. bimaculata*; 5 — *H. biumbrata*; 6 — *H. apicalis* (same in *H. mamaevi*).

Figs 7–11. *Homalocephala*, head left (7), same, anterior (8–9), head and thorax, left (10–11): 7–8 — *H. angustata*; 9 — *H. albitarsis*; 10 — *H. biumbrata*; 11 — *H. apicalis*.

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